

DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES OF NON-PROFIT SPORTS ASSOCIATION IN HAINAN PROVINCE, CHINA

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Abstract

Since the country has implemented the reform of the management of social organizations in the past 20 years, non-profit sports associations have flourished and played an important role in the implementation of the national fitness plan. However, after the decentralization of power, non-profit sports associations have exposed development difficulties. Therefore, I conducted a study on this. The purpose of this study is to: 1) To study the current situation and affecting factors strategies for development of the Non-Profit Sports Association in Hainan province; 2) To develop strategies for development of the Non-Profit Sports Association in Hainan province; 3) To assess the feasibility of implementing strategies for development of the Non-Profit Sports Association in Hainan province. This study adopts a combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods. Step 1: Through qualitative research, analyze and understand the development status and influencing factors of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, with a total of 10 respondents; Step 2: Through quantitative research, questionnaires were distributed to collect data, and structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for analysis, with a total of 374 respondents; Step 3: Through qualitative research, 10 experts were invited for focus group discussions. The results indicate that: 1) There are several key aspects in the development status of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province: first, the development goals of association organizers or managers are unclear; second, the association lacks funds; third, there is a lack of social services and fewer organized activities; fourth, human resource management is not standardized, especially the recruitment and training of volunteers lack long-term planning; fifth, the participation and satisfaction of members or participants in the association are insufficient; sixth, the association lacks long-term planning and governance means, and lacks fixed venues for activities. These current situations reflect the actual situation of the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. By comprehensively analyzing these factors, the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province can be further improved. 2) Stakeholders, human resources, funding, and social services have a significant positive impact on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. 3) It can be seen that this study has unanimously recognized the analysis of the development strategies of Non Profit Sports Association in Hainan Province, China. Moreover, the results of qualitative research have a certain degree of interpretability, and the structural equation model has good credibility and effectiveness, which has certain promotional value. Therefore, this study helps to understand the overall situation, influencing factors, model promotion, and application of development strategies of Non Profit Sports Association in Hainan Province,

China, laying a theoretical foundation for related research on development strategies of Non Profit Sports Association in Hainan Province, China.

Keywords: Development Strategies, Non-Profit Sports Associations, Stakeholders, Human Resources, Funding, Social Services.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the development strategy of Chinese sports organizations, non-profit sports associations are also an important part. The state has issued various policy documents on promoting the development of sports organizations, and issued the "Regulations on the Registration and Management of Social Groups" (2016) to standardize the construction of social organizations, accelerate the promotion of the national fitness plan, clarify the relationship between administrative departments and sports associations, promote the construction and development of various single sports associations, decentralize management authority, encourage social organizations to apply for various single sports associations, participate in the organization and management of government sports activities with non-profit sports associations, and implement and complete them in the form of government purchase of services by sports associations, etc.

According to statistics, from 2012 to 2017, the scale of registered sports social organizations in China increased from 23,000 to more than 48,000, with an average annual growth rate of more than 10%, which is much higher than the growth rate of about 4% of social organizations nationwide during the same period.

At present, Hainan has more than 90 provincial single sports associations, which are developing rapidly, and the development of individual associations has a great social influence. This paper analyzes the development status of Hainan's non-profit sports associations through research, finds development opportunities, explores the path of high-quality development of non-profit sports associations, and provides reference for future non-profit sports associations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The relationship between the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province and stakeholder factors

Stakeholders refer to actors who are interested in the topic under discussion, are affected by the topic, or have or may have an active or passive influence on the decision-making and implementation process due to their status. (Balane, 2020). Stakeholders refer to any group or individual who can influence or be influenced by the achievement of the company's goals (Grama-Vigouroux, 2020).

Stakeholders refer to individuals or groups that influence or are affected by the project process, content or results (Bahadorestani, 2020). Stakeholders refer to the goals, activities and influences of dealing with stakeholder relationships in an ethical, strategic or pragmatic way. (Kujala, 2022).

2.2 The relationship between the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province and human resource factors

Human resources refer to the total number of workers who have the ability to work mentally and physically and can promote the development of the entire economy and society, including both quantity and quality. (Huang, 2020). Human resources refer to the total labor capacity of people within a certain range, or in other words; it refers to the sum of mental and physical labor that can promote the development of the entire economy and society. (Shi, 2020).

Human resource managers should be good at training new employees, answering questions for new employees, and at the same time building career development channels for employees, providing training opportunities, fully tapping employees' potential, and mobilizing employees' enthusiasm. (Yang, Chen & Guo, 2022). Human resources are composed of managers, employees, users, and those being managed. (Wang, 2023).

2.3 The relationship between the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province and funding factors

Funding refers to the collective investment entity that invests in non-listed companies in the form of equity investment, profit sharing, and risk sharing (Liu, 2020). Funding refers to improving the diversified investment mechanism and encouraging social forces to participate in the construction of the public fitness service system (State Council, 2021).

Funding refers to making full use of local characteristic resources, vigorously developing the sports industry, cultivating new economic growth points, and providing necessary financial guarantees for achieving and maintaining equal sports public services for regional and urban and rural residents. (Zhu, 2022). Funding refers to the use of local community resources, social resources and government financial support to establish a diversified financing model. (Liu, 2023).

2.4 The relationship between the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province and social service factors

Social services refer to non-profit basic social services, which should be provided to all citizens as quasi-public goods (partly pure public goods) (Lin, 2022). Social service supply methods include: diversified supply, government purchase, and community service (Gao & Zhang, 2015).

With the development of society, the socialization of social services has promoted the emergence of the "social service state", which is considered to be a development form beyond the traditional welfare state, including non-profit sports associations purchasing government public sports services. (Lin, 2020).

2.5 Research Framework

This study takes stakeholders, human resources, funding, social services, and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province as dependent variables.

Based on the literature review and research objectives, this study constructs a development strategy model for non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. The figure is a schematic diagram of the model.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

The conceptual model gives the basic hypothesized relationship between stakeholder factors, human resource factors, funding factors, social services and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

The hypotheses are as follows:

- H1: Stakeholders affects the development strategy of the Hainan Non-profit Sports Association;
- H2: Human resource affects the development strategy of the non-profit sports association in Hainan Province;
- H3: Funding investment affects the development strategy of the Hainan Non-profit Sports Association;
- H4: Social service affects the development strategy of the non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The first step is to collect information through in-depth interviews to analyze the development status and influencing factors of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

The second step is to use the China Online Questionnaire Platform to collect data, and use SPSS and SmartPLS 4.0 software to process and analyze the data to construct an influencing factor model for the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

The sample data of this study comes from relevant personnel in the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. It is generally recommended that the sample size be at least 20 times (Lindeman et al., 1980), and the sample size is $17 \times 20 = 340$.

To ensure the comprehensiveness of the study, the actual distribution of the questionnaire should be greater than 340 copies. This survey adopts a simple random sampling method to select 374 people for questionnaire survey and collect data.

The third step is to use the focus group discussion method to test and confirm the influencing factors and structural equation model for the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Research status and influencing factors

4.1.1 Research status

1) Advantages: Both the Outline for Building a Powerful Sports Nation and the National Fitness Plan (2021-2025) propose to give full play to the demonstration role of national sports social organizations, promote the construction of sports federations at all levels, improve the national fitness organization network that covers urban and rural areas, is standardized and orderly, and is full of vitality, and drive all levels and types of single, industry, and group sports organizations to carry out national fitness activities. It is estimated that by 2025, the total scale of the sports industry will reach 5 trillion yuan.

2) Disadvantages: The lack of professional sports talents is an important factor restricting the development of non-profit sports associations, which is mainly reflected in two aspects. One is the lack of professional sports instructors; the other is the lack of professional sports management talents. In some organizations, one member wears multiple hats, leading to chaotic management, low organizational effectiveness, low employee motivation, and poor overall organizational development. (Li & Chen, 2023)

3) Opportunities: On September 2, 2014, the State Council executive meeting adopted specific measures to streamline administration and delegate power in the sports system, and made the decision to "cancel the approval of commercial and mass sports events." Shortly thereafter, the General Administration of Sports responded positively. In the reform of the event approval system, it officially issued a document canceling the approval of national sports events, including commercial and mass sports events, except for the National Comprehensive Games and a few special events. At this point, my country's sports social organizations have ushered in a good opportunity for independent development.

On October 20 of the same year, in the "Several Opinions on Accelerating the Development of the Sports Industry and Promoting Sports Consumption" issued by the State Council, the sports industry was elevated to a national strategy, and the market-oriented transformation of my country's sports became more obvious. Under the current social background of "industrialization and marketization", the construction of various sports social organizations at all levels in China will also face transformation opportunities. (Xiao, 2016)

4) Threats: Today, with the development of self-media, information spreads rapidly, and the way and scope of people's reception of information are also expanding. In other words, the operation management and social image of non-profit sports associations will be easy to understand. At the same time, non-profit sports associations are also being understood by some.

The impact of the image of non-standard sports organizations has caused people to resist the activities of non-profit sports associations, which has had a greater impact on the subsequent development of non-profit sports associations and ultimately required reshuffling and establishment.

Therefore, domestic scholars and experts also have concerns about non-profit sports associations. Concerns about the construction of social credibility, which is also a major obstacle and threat to the development of non-profit sports associations.

4.1.2 Influencing factors

Stakeholders: Stakeholders are important participants and supporters of non-profit sports associations. The participation and resource integration of stakeholders will affect the sustainability and quality of the development of non-profit sports associations.

Human resources: Human resources play an important role in the development of non-profit sports associations. Coaches, volunteers, members, etc. will affect the quality of non-profit sports associations.

Funding investment: Funding investment is the guarantee for the development of non-profit sports associations. Funding can guarantee the association's sports promotion, event development, and team training.

Social services: Social services are the key work of non-profit sports associations, carrying out national fitness activities and enhancing people's physical fitness.

Experts emphasized the importance of four key factors, namely stakeholders, human resources, funding, and social services, to the development of non-profit sports associations.

The views of these experts all emphasize the need to use national policies to cultivate sports professionals, actively promote sports, broaden funding channels, create classic sports events, introduce high-level talents, and standardize the management of associations. The comprehensive use of these factors can further promote the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

4.2 Develop strategies analysis

4.2.1 Variable description and Trust level analysis

Descriptive statistics were performed on the survey structure of the scale to determine the degree of influence of the scale name and the distribution of data. Most of the indicator variable data showed a normal distribution, and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of the main constructs and dimensions involved in this study were greater than 0.7, which met the corresponding judgment criteria, so the reliability of the sample scale was high.

4.2.2 Testing the reliability of the questionnaire

Table 1: second-order construct reliability test results table

Second-order construct	Number of measurement items	Cronbach's alpha(n=30)
Stakeholders	19	0.969
Human Resources	21	0.982
Funding investment	16	0.962
Social services	20	0.978
Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	14	0.966

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of each part is greater than 0.7, indicating that the questionnaire used in this study has good reliability.

4.2.3 Correlation analysis

A correlation analysis was conducted on variables such as stakeholders, human resources, funding, social services, and development strategies of Hainan Province's non-profit sports associations.

Table 2: HTMT criterion checklist for indicator variables in measurement models

Variable	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	M1		CT5
A1	1							
A2	0.727	1						
A3	0.805	0.872	1					
A4	0.552	0.59	0.754	1				
A5	0.338	0.351	0.452	0.885	1			
M1	0.477	0.441	0.494	0.843	0.87	1		
.....								
CT5	0.428	0.521	0.466	0.724	0.642	0.706		1

As can be seen from Table 2, the HTMT ratio is less than 1. According to the HTMT standard, the average correlation between different latent variables is much lower than the average correlation between the same latent variables, which indicates that each latent variable is a different latent variable with discriminant validity.

4.2.4 Complete collinearity

Table 3: Collinearity of each index of the measured variable

Topic	VIF
X11-STLP	1.939
X12-STAL	2.403
X13-STME	3.01
X14-STBM	1.461
X21-HRMAS	2.198
X22-HRMVO	2.877
X23-HRMSSI	1.662
X31-FIGEI	1.493
X32-FIITT	2.808
X33-FIISC	2.707
X41-SSGES	1.647
X42-SSCS	2.781
X43-SSVS	2.702
X44-SSSE	2.601
Y11-DSGE	2.67
Y12-DSIB	3.223
Y13-DSIC	2.286

As shown in Table 3, it can be seen that the internal VIF values of all latent variables in this study are less than 5. Therefore, it can be considered that there is no significant multicollinearity between the latent variables in this study, and the collinearity evaluation is passed.

4.2.5 Structural equation model

This study used SmartPLS4 to establish a path model and imported the collected 374 sample data into it.

Figure 2: Research path model diagram

4.2.6 Coefficient of determination - R²

Table 3: R² values of variables in the structural equation model of this study

Dimension	R-square	R-square adjusted
DSI	0.614	0.61

As can be seen from Table 4.10, the R² value of the Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association Development Strategy Model in the path model of this study is 0.614, indicating that the model has a good explanatory power for latent variables.

4.2.7 Effect size f²

Table 4: Predictive correlation f² values among 17 latent variables in the structural equation model of this study

	f-square	Result
Stakeholders->Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	0.047	Medium
Human Resources->Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	0.122	Medium
Funding->Development strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association	0.029	Medium
Social Services->Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	0.106	Medium

The f² value of the impact of stakeholder factors on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province is 0.047, the f² value of human resources factors is 0.122, the f² value of funding factors is 0.029, and the f² value of social service factors is 0.106, all of which are less than 0.15, the calculation results show that the predictive coefficients of the four variables for the dependent variable are all higher than 0.02, indicating that the predictive performance of the model is good.

4.2.8 Predictive relevance Q²

In the structural model, Q² represents the predicted correlation of the variable, and the larger the value, the stronger the predicted correlation.

Table 5: Predicted correlation scores

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	Result
DSI	1122	564.786	0.497	High

The calculation results show that the Q-square statistical correlation coefficient affecting the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province is 0.497, This indicates that the variable measurement tool has a high predictive effect on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

4.2.9 Significance of path coefficients

The structural equation model mainly uses non parametric Bootstrapping programs to detect the significance of coefficients.

Table 6: Results of significance test of path coefficient of structural equation model in this study

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Outcome
Stakeholders->Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	0.178	0.179	0.045	3.931	0.000	Supported
Human Resources->Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	0.328	0.328	0.051	6.413	0.000	Supported
Funding->Development strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association	0.173	0.172	0.043	3.627	0.000	Supported
Social Services->Development Strategy of Hainan Province Non-profit Sports Association of China	0.291	0.292	0.048	6.028	0.000	Supported

Note : NS=not significant, Not significant* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Since the t values of stakeholders, human resources, funding, and social services are all greater than 3.29, the P value is 0.000, the estimated value of the stakeholder factor is 0.179, the estimated value of the human resources factor is 0.328, the estimated value of the funding factor is 0.172, and the estimated value of the social service factor is 0.292, all path coefficients in the structural equation model are significant, and all hypotheses are supported.

4.3 Assess the feasibility

Examine and confirm the development strategy of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province through focus groups. This study convened a group of 10 industry stakeholders to summarize and verify the previous research. The group discussion was conducted by: 1) Leaders of Hainan Provincial Sports Administration Department, 2. 2) Heads of Hainan Provincial Non-profit Sports Associations, 4. 3) Experts and scholars from Hainan Provincial Colleges and Universities, 2. A total of 10 people were collected through purposeful random sampling. First, the researcher reported the results of the previous study and asked the group members individually. Second, the group members confirmed the research results and provided opinions through focus groups. Finally, the researcher collected the opinions of the group members on the results of the meeting discussion. Experts believe that the influencing factors and strategies are in line with the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. A focus group selection was established based on the target audience, taking into account the diversity of age, gender, participation, and loyalty. The validation process of this focus group includes discussion questions and suggestions on development strategies. Discussions and research are conducted from four aspects: stakeholders, human resources, financial investment, and social services. Through discussion, experts highly recognize the feasibility, suitability, practicality, and accuracy of development strategies. This is in line with the current development status of the non-profit sports association in Hainan Province, and the development strategy has high promotion value.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

5.1.1 Development Advantage

Non-profit sports associations should make full use of the national sports development policy, give full play to the flexibility, mobility, and mass advantages of non-profit sports associations, improve the forms of social sports participation, broaden the forms of participation under the form of "government-led-social participation", and use advantages to seek development.

5.1.2 Development disadvantage

Nonprofit sports associations have a single source of funding and a lack of funding, resulting in a lack of financial support for the cultivation of sports professionals, high turnover of full-time personnel in the association, and non-standard daily management of the association; Professional social sports instructors have not received sufficient training and the team is unstable. The association needs to actively integrate resources, strengthen the alliance between the association and enterprises, broaden the channels of resource sources, and change the phenomenon of single funding sources.

5.1.3 Development Opportunity

Under the "Sports Power" development strategy, the total scale of China's sports industry will reach 5 trillion yuan in 2025. Therefore, the association will take this opportunity to promote the organization of sports events and community activities, create brand events and activities, expand the influence of the association, expand the association's membership base, and lay a solid foundation for the development of the association.

5.1.4 Development threat

Non-profit sports associations are highly homogeneous, which further intensifies competition. The lack of government supervision and management and professionalism have led to a decline in the social credibility of associations and a decrease in public participation, posing a threat to non-profit sports associations, making it difficult for the associations to develop.

5.2 Discussion

5.2.1 The relationship between stakeholders and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, china

This study aims to explore the relationship between stakeholder factors and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. The results of this study confirm the view of H1 of this study and prove the positive impact of stakeholder factors on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. Wang & Tao (2018) Strengthen the supervision of sports associations by civil affairs departments on the compliance of sports associations with the charter, so that the corporate governance of sports associations has rules to follow; implement democratic election systems and expand the scope of membership to improve the corporate governance of sports associations.

5.2.2 The relationship between human resources and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, China

This study aims to explore the relationship between human resources and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. The results of this study confirm the view of H2 of this study and prove the positive impact of human resources on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. The association provides professional instructors, coaches, and managers, vigorously promotes sports activities, and creates a good exercise atmosphere. (Sun, 2019)

5.2.3 The relationship between funding and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, China

This study aims to explore the relationship between funding and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. The results of this study confirm the view of H3 of this study and prove the positive impact of funding on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. Ma (2021) encourages the government to purchase public sports services and increase investment in social sports organizations.

5.2.4 The relationship between social services and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, China

This study aims to explore the relationship between social services and the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. The results of this study confirm the view of H4 of this study and prove the positive impact of social services on the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province. Giving full play to the role of grassroots sports associations in serving the society is an important direction for the development of sports social organizations in the new era. (Fu & Xun,2022)

5.3 Suggestion

This study combines the development status of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, starting from factors such as stakeholders, human resources, funding, and social services, analyzes the development status of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province, studies its influencing factors. Finally, the development strategy of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province is proposed. Reflected as: standardize the legal person governance association system, reasonably integrate social resources, and attract people with lofty ideals to participate in the management of the association; in terms of human resource management, it is recommended to cultivate a coaching team and a relatively fixed volunteer team, and guide high-level athletes or sports enthusiasts to join the association; expand multi-channel and multi-method fund preparation, integrate enterprises and associations, governments and associations, and solve funding problems by providing services. Strengthen the social service work of the association, actively face the masses, provide services, strengthen sports into the community, campus, and enterprises, create brand sports events, and attract more people to participate in association activities. Subsequent research suggests adding or replacing variables in the research model so that the model can more comprehensively reflect the factors affecting the development of non-profit sports associations in Hainan Province.

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